

Estimation of mesalazine in tablet matrix using densitometric chromatography

Amit Das, Anupal Chowdhury, Plaban Bhattacharya and Achintya Saha*

Department of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : achintya_saha@yahoo.com Fax : 91-33-23519755

Manuscript received 01 June 2011, accepted 07 September 2011

Abstract : Mesalazine (5-amino salicylic acid, MZ) is used for the treatment of inflammatory bowel diseases. It is a polar compound and exhibited amphoteric property. A miniaturized method of quantification in tablet formulation is developed using thin layer chromatography (HPTLC). Prechromatographic derivatization is carried out by reacting the sample with *p*-dimethyl-amino-benzaldehyde (DMAB) in methanolic HCl. Definite volumes of developed yellow colored solution is applied on silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ TLC plate. The mobile phase for optimum resolution is explored with toluene : ethyl acetate : methanol (4 : 1 : 1) solvent system, and a distinct compact spot of MZ is observed at *R_f* 0.65 on detection wavelength of 350 nm. LOD and LOQ are estimated to be 0.62 and 2.06 pmol mL⁻¹ of MZ. Standard calibration curve is prepared in the range of 6.54 to 39.24 pmol mL⁻¹ with *r*² > 0.99. The developed method is found to be precise and accurate, and might be useful in routine quality control.

Keywords : Mesalazine, quantitative analysis, HPTLC, tablet formulation.

Introduction

Mesalazine (MZ, CAS 89-57-6) is widely used for the treatment of ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease¹. It generally acts to inhibit local prostaglandin and leukotriene syntheses in the gastrointestinal mucosa². It is very important to determine the quantity of MZ in its dosage forms in order to check batch to batch content uniformity. Mass spectroscopy³ and HPLC⁴ analyses are reported for determination of MZ. UV-spectrophotometric method is also explored in three simple sensitive methods for development of colored chromogens⁵. But the results obtained of those methods are found to be unsatisfactory when the tablet dosage form is analyzed⁵. The reagent preparation steps are cumbersome and no calibration range is monitored.

Estimation of MZ by densitometric TLC (HPTLC) is not reported earlier. HPTLC technique is carried out within a short period of time; it requires few mobile phases, and allows the analysis of a large number of samples simultaneously. The ability of HPTLC to analyze many samples in parallel has the advantage over other techniques because the separation of 10 or 20 samples takes the same time as the separation of one sample⁶. In the present study an attempt has been made to develop a robust assay method of MZ in tablet matrix by HPTLC.

Results and discussion

Isolation and identification of MZ :

MZ is isolated from commercial tablets (Mesacol[®], Sun Pharmaceuticals) and identified by spectral analyses⁴. The average melting point is found to be 276 °C. Samples dissolved in methanolic HCl are observed λ_{\max} at 208, 229 and 301 nm with log ϵ of 3.20, 2.73 and 2.45 respectively. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, 0.1% DCl in CD₃OD, I.S. DSS) revealed characteristic spectral shifts at 7.96 (1H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz, H6), 7.60 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 3.0 Hz, H4) and 7.14 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H3) confirmed the purity of the compound (MZ) isolated from the tablet matrix.

Pre-chromatographic derivatization and calibration range selection :

In order to validate an efficient method for the analysis of MZ in tablet matrix, preliminary tests are performed with the objective to select adequate and optimum conditions. Parameters, such as reagent-sample ratio, detection wavelength, ideal mobile phases and their proportions, and the concentration range of the standard solutions are exhaustively studied.

For derivatization, *p*-dimethyl-amino-benzaldehyde (DMAB) dissolved in methanolic HCl (2.5%) is used as

reagent and mixed with sample in ratio of 1 : 9 at room temperature. A solvent system consisting of toluene : ethyl acetate: methanol (4 : 1 : 1) is used as optimum mobile phase and separation is achieved without interference of tablet matrix components. Length of chromatogram development is 7 cm in about 15 min.

Standard calibration curve is prepared in the range of 6.54 to 65.4 pmol mL⁻¹ of MZ with $r^2 > 0.99$. Derivatized samples are spotted on silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ precoated plate, and eluted with mobile phase saturated for 30 min. After drying the plate is scanned at 350 nm and a compact spot of MZ is observed at R_f 0.65 (Fig. 1a). The system calibration is performed by analyzing six standards and three samples simultaneously (Fig. 1b). Derivatized standard and samples are eluted at the same R_f , observing superimposable spectra (Fig. 1c).

Validation parameters :

Linearity :

The standard curve of MZ is linear over the concentration range of 6.54–65.4 pmol mL⁻¹ (11.4, 22.8, 45.6, 57, 91.2 and 114 pg/spot). Each solution is spotted six times. This range includes the solution concentration of the tablet. The calibration curve for MZ has a correlation coefficient (r^2) of 0.99 ± 0.001 , indicating a linear relationship between the concentration of MZ and peak area over the range investigated. The slope of the curve is 57.19 ± 1.77 and the intercept is 1330.67 ± 135.36 .

Limit of detection and limit of quantification (LOD and LOQ) :

LOD and LOQ are determined using the linear regression equations⁷ : $LOD = 3 S_{y,x}/b$ and $LOQ = 10 S_{y,x}/b$, where $S_{y,x}$ is the relative standard deviation (RSD) of the Y-value distribution around the regression line and b is the slope of the calibration curve. Mean RSD of the six calculated concentration ($n = 5$) is found to be 1.78 and the slope of calibration curve is 56.41. The LOD and LOQ are found to be 0.62 and 2.06 pmol/mL respectively.

Precision :

Repeatability is determined by the measurement of instrumental and intra-assay precision. Instrumental precision is measured in ten spots of the standard at three different concentrations (6.54, 32.7 and 65.4 pmol/mL).

Fig. 1. (a) Representative chromatogram of derivatized MZ (32.7 pmol/mL), (b) quantitative determination of MZ in tablets, track 1 to 6 : standard 11.4, 22.8, 45.6, 57, 91.2 and 114 pg and track 7 to 10 : samples, (c) spectral comparison of standard and sample.

The repeatability or intra-assay precision is studied by analyzing on the same day, five solutions of three concentrations (2, 4 and 8 ng/mL) from pharmaceutical samples, each of which is independently prepared and

being applied five times. Intermediate precision (inter-assay precision) included analyses at the same three concentrations; each solution is analyzed three times on the same day for three different days.

Precision analysis studies showed an instrumental precision between 0.38 and 2.01%; an intra-assay variation between 0.51 and 1.25% and an inter-assay variation between 0.99 and 2.55% (Table 1). The values are adequate for the analysis of drugs in concentration as low as picogram. All the values for intra-assay precision are under 2% of coefficient of variance (CV), and only one mean value for instrumental precision is above 1%, indicating the maintenance of precision criteria⁸ for instrumental (<1%) and intra-assay (<2%) precision.

Table 1. Precision of the method, CV (%)

Concentration (pmol/mL)	Instrumental precision ^a	Intra-assay precision ^b	Intermediate precision ^c
6.54	2.01	1.25	2.55
32.7	0.63	0.89	1.77
65.4	0.38	0.51	0.99

^aAnalyzed on the same day ($n = 10$).

^bAnalyzed on the same day ($n = 5$ for each concentration).

^cAnalyzed on three different days ($n = 15$ for each concentration), CV = Coefficient of variance.

Accuracy :

The accuracy is determined by standard addition, applying the method to pharmaceutical preparations to which 6.54, 32.7 and 65.4 pmol/mL of standard substances are added in the samples. The accuracy is then calculated from the test results as the percentage of analyte recovered by the assay. The recovery, i.e. the difference between results of study and 100% recovery, is not differ from the real value in more than 2%, and is independent of the concentration with a CV less than 1.58% as shown in Table 2.

Robustness :

The robustness is evaluated by an intentional minor modification in the composition of the mobile phase used in the proposed method. The tested mobile phase is toluene/ethyl acetate/methanol (3 : 1 : 1, by vol.). The comparison of the values from the two mobile phases suggests that the proposed method is robust under mobile phase variations.

Table 2. Method accuracy

Added concentration (pmol/mL)	Estimated concentration (pmol/mL) ^a	Accuracy (%) ^b	CV (%)
6.54	6.58 ± 0.34	100.61	0.79
32.7	32.59 ± 2.56	99.66	0.24
65.4	64.36 ± 5.02	98.41	0.12
Inter-assay ($n = 27$)			
6.54	6.45 ± 0.66	98.66	1.58
32.7	32.05 ± 3.84	98.00	0.37
65.4	64.33 ± 4.22	98.37	0.10

^aMean ± SD.

^b(Observed concentration/original added concentration) × 100.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

HPTLC system, Spectrodensitometer Scanner 3 Camag (Muttenz, Switzerland)⁹ equipped with the software winCATS 1.4.1¹⁰ (Camag) are used for densitometric chromatography. Band application device-Linomat 5 automatic (Camag)¹¹, twin-trough chromatographic chamber (Camag) and HPTLC plates precoated with silica gel F 254 (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) are used for chromatogram development.

Reagents and chemicals :

HPLC grade solvents are used for analysis. All of the reagents are proanalysis quality. Tablet of MZ (Mesacol®, Sun Pharmaceuticals) is purchased from a local drug store.

Methods :

Isolation and identification of MZ :

Five tablets are powdered and suspended in 200 mL 10% dilute HCl solution. The resultant dispersion is sonicated for 1 h followed by filtration. The clear filtrate is collected and pH is adjusted to 4–5 with NaOH. A buff colored precipitate is observed, refiltration to collect the solid residue, dried at 100 °C for 1 h. The purity of the compound is checked by melting point, UV and NMR spectroscopic analyses.

Standard solution preparation :

A stock solution of MZ is prepared quantitatively in 10% methanolic HCl to a concentration of 1 mg/mL. Working solutions of analyte are prepared by appropriate dilutions of the stock solution with methanol.

Sample preparation :

Pharmaceutical preparation, 20 tablets containing 400

mg of MZ each, are weighed and ground into fine powder, and an accurately weighed portion equivalent to 40 mg of MZ is dispersed to 100 mL with 10% methanolic HCl. The solution is centrifuged and the supernatant is used for analysis. Appropriate dilutions are incorporated for validation of the method.

Reagent preparation :

Subsequent heating after addition of reagent in the sample is reported⁵ for estimation of MZ in tablet dosage. In this work, we managed to simplify that method. Materials for reagent preparation are modified and is prepared without any requirement of heat. The reagent is prepared freshly for each set of analysis. Different solvent, acid and quantities of DMAB are tried to stabilize the reagent preparations, which stable for a week at 26 °C. Briefly 2.5 mL of concentrated HCl is added dropwise to 97.5 mL methanol placed on a magnetic stirrer at 26 °C. 500 mg DMAB is dissolved in the prepared acidic methanol solution (2.5%).

Pre-chromatographic derivatization :

Samples are derivatized instantly with the DMAB reagent at room temperature at the sample-reagent ratio of 1 : 9.

Chromatographic conditions :

Chromatography is performed on preactivated TLC plates (10 cm × 10 cm or 20 cm × 10 cm). The plates are washed with methanol and activated at 120 °C for 20 min. Derivatized standard and sample solutions are applied in the form of band at 15 mm from the lower edge using a 100 µL syringe (Hamilton, Bonaduz, Switzerland) by Linomat V sample applicator¹¹. Linear ascending development is carried out in pre-saturated (optimized to 30 min for better resolution) vertical twin trough glass chambers (10 cm × 10 cm or 20 cm × 10 cm) saturated with the mobile phase. Several binary or ternary eluents are tested using different proportions of solvents, such as dichloro-methane, methanol, isopropanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, glacial acetic acid, toluene, water, *n*-butanol and ammonia. After development, plates are dried, scanned and quantified densitometrically at 350 nm (maximum wavelength in the spectra of the derivative). A deuterium lamp is used as the radiation source. TLC Scanner-III controlled by winCATS 1.4.1.8154 software¹⁰ (Camag) is used for quantitative evaluation. The densitometry scan-

ning is performed in the reflectance/absorbance mode, slit width 3.00 mm × 0.45 mm, scanning speed 20 mm/sec and data resolution 10 µm/step. Savitsky-Golay-7¹⁰ is used for data filtering and the lowest slope for baseline correction in order to integrate the area. Quantification is performed using linear regression equations of derivatized standard MZ.

Validation :

The parameters used for method validation are linearity, precision, accuracy and robustness. Validation is performed in compliance with international standards⁸. All data are evaluated using standard statistical packages. Statistical significance is considered at 95% probability level ($p < 0.05$), Pearson's coefficient (r^2) is used to evaluate significance of correlations. Working stock solution is prepared by dilution with methanol to give the compound concentrations 6.54, 13.08, 26.16, 32.7, 52.32 and 65.4 pmol mL⁻¹. Standard solution is spotted on TLC plate at 11.4, 22.8, 45.6, 57, 91.2 and 114 pg/spot. Each concentration is spotted six times. The calibration curves are prepared by the least-square method using absolute amount (pg/band) as independent variable (X) and the peak area of standards as dependent variable (Y). Regression analysis test is performed. The selection of working concentration range is based on their response. Linearity of the curve (r^2), slope and intercept are noted and standard error of mean is calculated. The LOD is calculated⁷ at the lowest concentration of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantified as an exact value. The LOQ is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be quantitatively determined⁷ with suitable precision and accuracy.

The repeatability of the measurement ($n = 10$) of peak area of MZ standards are expressed in terms of % CV. The intra- and inter-assay variations are also checked. Recovery study, i.e. the accuracy of the developed method is assessed by addition of a known quantity of standard followed by estimation. Robustness is measured for susceptibility of the method to small changes that might occur during routine analysis, like small changes of pH values, mobile phase composition and laboratory temperature.

Conclusion :

The results indicate that the proposed densitometric

Note

TLC method is useful for the determination of MZ in tablet matrix. The method has the required linearity, precision, accuracy, detection and quantification limits needed for the quantitative estimation of MZ in tablet dosage form. Additionally the method is fast, simple, efficient, and easy to perform. HPTLC separation is obtained within 10 min and allows for a large number of samples to be measured simultaneously with a very good accuracy, sensitivity and precision which is very important especially in quality control.

The procedure works without separation steps, only by centrifugation, because the excipients do not dissolve in the working solvent. Therefore, the proposed method might be choice for the quantitative analysis of MZ in tablet dosage form.

Acknowledgement

The financial assistance received from University Potential of Excellence Scheme of UGC is thankfully acknowledged.

References

1. K. Parfitt, "Martindale – The Complete Drug Reference", 32nd ed., Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1999, p. 1199.
2. S. M. Greenfield, N. A. Punchard, J. P. Teare and R. P. H. Thompson, *Aliment. Pharmacol. Ther.*, 1993, **7**, 369.
3. E. Pastorini, M. Locatelli, P. Simoni, G. Roda, E. Roda and A. Roda, *J. Chromatogr. B : Analyt. Technol. Biomed. Life Sci.*, 2008, **872**, 99.
4. M. Nobilis, Z. Vybiralova, K. Sladkova, M. Lisa, M. Holcapek and J. Kvetina, *J. Chromatogr. A*, 2006, **1119**, 299.
5. K. M. Patel, C. N. Patel, B. Panigrahi, A. S. Parikh and H. N. Patel, *J. Young Pharm.*, 2010, **2**, 284.
6. A. Mohammad and M. Luqman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 55.
7. F. T. Peters and H. H. Maurer, *Accred. Qual. Assur.*, 2002, **7**, 441.
8. G. Shabir, *J. Chromatogr. A*, 2003, **987**, 57.
9. <http://www.camag.com/tlc-scanner.html>
10. <http://www.camag.com/wincats/>
11. <http://www.camag.com/linomat5.html>

